

Trends of Breeding Birds in the Wadden Sea 1991–2013

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Progress Report Trends of Breeding Birds in the Wadden Sea 1991 – 2013

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Content

1 Introduction	5
2 Methods	7
3 Overview trilateral and regional trends	9
4 Species accounts	15
4.1 Great Cormorant	17
4.2 Eurasian Spoonbill	18
4.3 Common Shelduck	19
4.4 Common Eider	20
4.5 Red-breasted Merganser	21
4.6 Hen Harrier	22
4.7 Eurasian Oystercatcher	23
4.8 Pied Avocet	24
4.9 Great Ringed Plover	25
4.10 Kentish Plover	26
4.11 Northern Lapwing	27
4.12 Black-tailed Godwit	28
4.13 Eurasian Curlew	29
4.14 Common Redshank	30
4.15 Mediterranean Gull	31
4.16 Common Black-headed Gull	32
4.17 Common Gull	33
4.18 Lesser Black-backed Gull	34
4.19 Herring Gull	35
4.20 Great Black-backed Gull	36
4.21 Gull-billed Tern	37
4.22 Sandwich Tern	38
4.23 Common Tern	39
4.24 Arctic Tern	40
4.25 Little Tern	41
4.26 Short-eared Owl	42
5 Total counts rare species	43
6 References	44
Annex1 Species according to habitats and food	45
Annex 2 Counting units in the Wadden Sea	47
Annex 3 List of census areas	48
Annex 4 Counting coverage of census areas	51
Annex 5 Species list	51

Monitoring breeding birds, the JMBB program

The Wadden Sea supports large numbers of breeding birds and 10–12 million of migratory birds. For several breeding bird species like Eurasian Spoonbill, Oystercatcher, Avocet, Kentish Plover, Common Redshank, Lesser Black-backed Gull, Gull-billed Tern and Sandwich Tern, the Wadden Sea is among the most important breeding sites in Northwest-Europe. Several species are included in Annex I of the EU-Bird Directive or listed as Species of European Concern (SPEC). At national level, many Wadden Sea breeding birds represent an important share of national breeding bird populations and are listed as Red List species.

Monitoring of breeding birds in the Wadden Sea has been carried out by the Joint Monitoring Group for Breeding Birds (JMBB) in the framework of the Trilateral Monitoring and Assessment Program (TMAP) since 1991 (Fleet et al., 1994; Melter et al., 1997; Rasmussen et al., 2000; Koffijberg et al., 2006). The monitoring scheme currently focuses on 35 bird species that are considered characteristic for the Wadden Sea ecosystem (Tab. A.4.1). Common breeding birds (8 species) are counted annually in a network of census areas, distributed over all regions and habitats of the

Wadden Sea Area. Colonial and rare breeding birds (27 species) are difficult to survey with census areas and are counted by annual complete counts in the entire Wadden Sea. Once every 5 years, a total count of all species, including common species, is carried out (1991, 1996, 2001, 2006, 2012; interval changed to once every 6 years according to EC Birds Directive reporting). The monitoring scheme aims to assess and detect population size, distribution and population trends in Wadden Sea breeding birds. Fieldwork is standardised and carried out according to trilaterally harmonised methods (Hälterlein et al., 1995) by nearly 500 ornithologists, mainly consisting of staff of NGOs, governmental bodies, site managers and volunteers. A so-called Quality Assurance Meeting (QAM) is organised regularly to provide a platform for exchange of field experience among counters and discussion of specific counting pitfalls (e.g. Blew, 2003).

This progress report aims to present a regular update of trends in breeding bird numbers, for those species where trend calculations are possible (at the moment 26 species) and that have been monitored from 1991 onwards. The report includes the description of methods, an overview on trilateral and regional trends, trend sheets on 26 breeding bird species and detailed information on census sites.

Drawing:
Niels Knudsen

Photo:
Gundolf Reichert

2 Methods

Introduction

As part of the JMBB program, 35 breeding birds species are currently being monitored in the Wadden Sea, of which 26 are presented here with overall and national trends. Trends are shown for (A) the Wadden Sea Area, (B) Denmark, (C) the federal state of Schleswig-Holstein (Germany), (D) the federal states of Niedersachsen/Hamburg (Germany) and (E) The Netherlands. More information on counting units can be found in Annex 2 and 3. For a selection of 15 abundant species also regional trends are presented on a map of the Wadden Sea. These regional trends have been added in this report as they provide a good indicator of changes in local numbers, which can be more easily linked with changes in environmental conditions and other local drivers. National trends on the other hand, give a more comprehensive overview in changes in bird populations, not necessarily driven by ecological changes, but just representing political borders. For regional trends, the Wadden Sea has been divided in 7 regions, in which also estuarine (Ems, Weser-Elbe) and non-estuarine regions have been separated (Fig. 3.2).

For very rare species, total numbers from the total counts in 1991–2006 are shown in a separate account. Data from total counts only give a limited overview of trends, as there has been only one count every 5–6 years. Total counts primarily aim to assess total population size and distribution.

Data and methods

For rare and colonial breeding birds annual counts have been carried out in all years, and their numbers are summarized for 56 census regions in the international Wadden Sea (Fig. A.2.1). Occasional missing counts, were estimated by the national co-ordinators, by using counts from other years and/or expert judgement (this usually applies to < 5% of the collected data). Abundant species, for which total counts are only carried out once every 6 years, trends are derived from annually counted sample sites, so-called census areas. This dataset contains an internationally agreed network of 103 representative census areas, spread equally over the international Wadden Sea. For The Netherlands, 245 additional census areas have been used that are counted frequently in the framework of the Dutch Common Bird Census (BMP) of the national surveillance scheme 'Netwerk Ecologische Monitoring'. On occasions where a census area was not counted in a certain year, data have been imputed by the commonly used TRIM package (Trends and Indices in Monitoring data; Pannekoek & van Strien, 1999). For this imputing, missing data are estimated with help of available data elsewhere in the region (separation after 7 regions, see above).

With the trend update from 1991–2011 onwards, trends have been calculated by CBS Statistics Netherlands. Trends are calculated at the level of 7 the distinguished regions (see above), from which then national trends and the trend for the international Wadden Sea are derived. In order to compensate for the large number

Trend classification	Trend description	Population change
	strong increase	sign. increase of >5% per year
	moderate increase	sign. increase of <5% per year
	stable	no significant population change
	moderate decrease	sign. decrease of <5% per year
	strong decrease	sign. decrease of >5% per year
	uncertain	no reliable trend classification possible (mostly due to strong fluctuations)
	data do not allow trend analysis	

Table 2.1
Trend classification, used to describe trends of breeding birds and migratory birds in The Wadden Sea. The colours which are used to depict trends are used throughout this report.

of census areas in The Netherlands, trends for abundant species have been weighted according to the distribution of those species in 2006 (data derived from the total count). Due to this slightly different approach of trend calculations, annual indices may be not entirely identical to those published before.

Trend analysis is carried out with the TRIM package (see above). Trends are tested for significance at $P = 0.05$ with a Wald-test. Annual indices are presented relative to the base year 1996 (set at 100). Exceptions are species which did not occur in 1996 (e.g. Eurasian Spoonbill in Schleswig-Holstein). In such occasions, the base year is set at the last year of the data series.

For a proper assessment of the trends, a standardized trend classification is used (identical to that in migratory birds) (Tab. 1.1). In addition to the data for 1991–2011, in Denmark and The Netherlands annual indices up to 2013 are presented as well. These are only shown in the graphs (to show the most recent data available). The trend assessments always cover the period 1991–2011 in order to keep the period similar to all regions and all countries.

Acknowledgements

Fieldwork for breeding birds is carried out by a large number of people, including staff from NGOs and local conservation agencies, (local) governmental bodies, volunteer bird watchers and professional bird counters. Current organization and co-ordination for Denmark is done by University of Aarhus (Aarhus), for Schleswig-Holstein by the National Park Agency 'Schleswig-Holsteinisches Wattenmeer' (Tönning), for Niedersachsen and Hamburg by the National Park Administration 'Niedersächsisches Wattenmeer' (Wilhelmshaven) and in The Netherlands by SOVON Dutch Centre for Field Ornithology (Nijmegen), commissioned by the Ministry of Economical Affairs and Rijkswaterstaat, as part of the national ecological surveillance scheme NEM.

Photo:
Bo Lassen Christiansen

3 Overview trilateral and regional trends

This chapter gives an overview of general trends on the level of the trilateral Wadden Sea, the four countries (Denmark, Schleswig-Holstein, Niedersachsen/Hamburg and the Netherlands) and on the level of seven regions (Fig. 3.2). This overview aims to present an overall impression of trends for each species, and similarities or differences within the Wadden Sea. Especially the regional trends may provide a good indicator of

significantly decreased in the long-term trend since 1991, among them typical Wadden Sea breeders such as Kentish Plover, Great Ringed Plover, Hen Harrier, Avocet, Common Tern, Common Redshank, Oystercatcher and Common Eider. Dunlin, Ruff and Common Snipe already went down before the monitoring in the Wadden Sea started, and meanwhile have become so rare and scattered breeders that an analysis of their trend

Figure 3.1
Summary of trends in breeding birds in the Wadden Sea 1991-2011. Shown is the mean annual population change in %, ranked from increasing species (top) to decreasing species (bottom), and based on the output of the TRIM-analysis. Dunlin, Ruff and Common Snipe have become so rare that their annual decline was arbitrarily set at -15%.

changes in local numbers and eventually point at local drivers causing these changes. Regional trends have been included only for a selection of 15 more or less abundant and widely distributed species. They are plotted on a map to highlight regional differences.

A summary of trends for all species for which trends could be calculated (29 out of the 35 monitored species) shows that 15 species have

after 1991 is not possible. Among the thriving species are mainly colonial breeding birds, like Mediterranean Gull (a 'new' species that is currently expanding its breeding range), Great Cormorant, Eurasian Spoonbill, Great Black-backed Gull and Lesser Black-backed Gull.

Table 3.1
Trends until 2011 –given for the entire period since 1991 and for the last ten years (to allow comparison between recent changes and long-term trend). Species are sorted by their euring code.

Species	Long-term 21-years trend 1991 - 2011					Short-term 10-years trend 2002 - 2011				
	WS	DK	SH	Nds/ HH	NL	WS	DK	SH	Nds/ HH	NL
Great Cormorant	↑↑	—	↑	↑	↑↑	↑	—	—	—	↑
Eurasian Spoonbill	↑↑	—	↑↑	↑↑	↑↑	↑↑	—	↑↑	↑↑	↑
Shelduck	↑	↑	↑	→	↑	→	—	—	—	↑
Common Eider	↓	↑↑	↓↓	↑	↓	↓	↑↑	↓	—	↓↓↓
Red-breasted Merganser	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Hen Harrier	↓	—	—	→	↓↓↓	↓↓↓	—	—	↓	↓↓↓
Oystercatcher	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	—	↓	↓	↓
Avocet	↓	↓	→	↓	↓↓↓	↓	—	—	↓	↓↓↓
Great Ringed Plover	↓	↓	↓	↓↓↓	↓	—	—	—	—	—
Kentish Plover	↓	↑	↓	↓↓↓	↓	→	—	—	↓↓↓	—
Northern Lapwing	↓	↓	↓	↓	→	↓	—	↓	↓	→
Black-tailed Godwit	↓	↓	—	↓	↓	↓	—	↓	↓	→
Eurasian Curlew	↓	—	—	—	↓	→	—	—	—	→
Common Redshank	↓	↓	→	↓	↓	↓	↓↓↓	→	→	→
Mediterranean Gull	↑↑	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	→	—
Black-headed Gull	↓	—	→	↓	↓	—	—	—	↓	—
Common Gull	↑	↑	↑	↑↑	↓	↓	↓	→	—	↓↓↓
Lesser Black-backed Gull	↑↑	↑↑	↑↑	↑↑	↑	↑	↑	→	—	—
Herring Gull	↓	↑	→	↓	↓	↓	↑	↓	↓↓↓	→
Great Black-backed Gull	↑↑	—	↑↑	—	—	↑	—	↑	—	—
Gull-billed Tern	—	—	—	↓	—	—	—	—	—	—
Sandwich Tern	→	↑↑	↓↓↓	—	↑	—	↑↑	↓↓↓	—	—
Common Tern	↓	↓	—	↓	↓	↓	—	—	—	↓
Arctic Tern	↓	→	→	↓	↓	↓	—	—	—	↓
Little Tern	→	↑	↓	↓	↑	—	—	—	—	—
Short-eared Owl	↓	—	—	→	↓	↓	—	—	—	—

strong increase
 moderate increase
 stable
 data do not allow trend analysis
 strong decrease
 moderate decrease
 uncertain

WS - Wadden Sea; DK - Denmark; SH - Schleswig-Holstein; Nds/HH - Niedersachsen/Hamburg; NL - The Netherlands

Figure 3.2
Seven regions of the Wadden Sea of where the available data allowed a statistical trend analysis in 4 categories. Percentages represent mean annual population change but are not given for stable and uncertain trends.

Figure 3.3 - 3.6
Regional trends of breeding bird species in the Wadden Sea 1991-2011.

Figure 3.7 - 3.12
Regional trends of breeding
bird species in the Wadden
Sea 1991-2011.

Figure 3.13 - 3.17
Regional trends of breeding
bird species in the Wadden
Sea 1991-2011.

In all habitats concerned (coastal grassland, beach & offshore, dunes and salt marsh) about 60% of the breeding bird species (relation to species in Annex 1) are in moderate decline. Among birds of coastal grasslands and birds of salt marshes the largest proportion of declining species is found.

Figures 3.18-3.19
Trend status of species in different breeding habitats for the periods 1991-2011 (left) and 2002-2011 (right).

- increase or stable
- moderate decline
- steep decline
- unclear

Large differences in trend status in dependence of food choice exist (relation to species in Annex 1). In breeding birds species depending on fish and shrimps (mainly Great Cormorant and Eurasian Spoonbill) are doing much better than species depending on invertebrates which include both increasing and decreasing species. Breeding birds feeding on invertebrates and showing declines can be found at salt marshes, tidal areas and agricultural grasslands.

Figures 3.20-3.21
Trend status of species differing in food choice for the periods 1991-2011 (left) and 2002-2011 (right)

- increase or stable
- moderate decline
- steep decline
- unclear

4.1 Great Cormorant

Phalacrocorax carbo

00720

DK: Skarv

D: Kormoran

NL: Aalscholver

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Figures 4.1.1-4.1.2 The left figure represent the trend of Great Cormorant in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

The right figure shows the total count of Great Cormorant in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

Explanatory Note

Great Cormorant although only a small part of the NW-European population is breeding in the Wadden Sea, the species is still increasing. This is in contrast with numbers outside the breeding season, which mainly originate from the large inland colonies, where numbers tend to stabilize. Recently, numbers in Niedersachsen and The Netherlands also show signs of saturation. The Netherlands and Niedersachsen support the largest colonies. Schleswig-Holstein (1997) and Denmark (2003) were colonized later on. Nearly all colonies are situated at islands or artificial offshore structures (platforms, etc.).

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

Figures 4.1.3-4.1.6 The figures represent the trends of Great Cormorant in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↑↑	↑
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↑	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↑	—
(F) The Netherlands		↑↑	↑

↑↑ strong increase ↓↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain — data do not allow trend analysis

Figure 4.1.7 Total counts of Great Cormorant in the international Wadden Sea.

4.2 Eurasian Spoonbill

01440

Platalea leucorodia

DK: Skestork

D: Löffler

NL: Lepelaar

Figures 4.2.1-4.2.2
The left figure represent the trend of Eurasian Spoonbill in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.
The right figure shows the total count of Eurasian Spoonbill in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Explanatory Note

In line with the numbers outside the breeding season, Eurasian Spoonbill experienced strong increase in all parts of the Wadden Sea. Since the area was initially colonized from The Netherlands, highest numbers still breed west of the River Elbe. Schleswig-Holstein was colonised in 2000, Denmark in 2007. Further increases are expected, although in The Netherlands also signs of saturation appear. Colonies are mainly found at the islands, both in dune areas and on salt marshes.

Figures 4.2.3-4.2.6
The figures represent the trends of Eurasian Spoonbill in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot; 2001 for SH). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figure 4.2.7 (right)
Total counts of Eurasian Spoonbill in the international Wadden Sea.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↑↑	↑↑
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↑↑	↑↑
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↑↑	↑↑
(F) The Netherlands		↑↑	↑

↑ ↑ strong increase
 ↓ ↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain
 — data do not allow trend analysis

4.3 Common Shelduck

Tadorna tadorna

01730

DK: Gravand

D: Brandgans

NL: Bergeend

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Explanatory Note

Numbers of Common Shelduck have increased on the long term, but have stabilized recently. Part of the fluctuations shown is probably due to census problems, as the species is notorious difficult to count and not all birds present do actually breed. The species is mainly breeding in rabbit holes (dunes areas) and in e.g. deserted buildings (mainland).

Figures 4.3.1-4.3.2 The left figure represent the trend of Common Shelduck in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

The right figure shows the total count of Common Shelduck in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figures 4.3.3-4.3.6 The figures represent the trends of Common Shelduck in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↑	→
(C) Denmark		↑	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↑	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	—
(F) The Netherlands		↑	↑

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain — data do not allow trend analysis

Figure 4.3.7 Total counts of Common Shelduck in the international Wadden Sea.

4.4 Common Eider

02060

Somateria mollissima

DK: Ederfugl

D: Eiderente

NL: Eidereend

Figures 4.4.1-4.4.2
The left figure represent the trend of Common Eider in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.
The right figure shows the total count of Common Eider in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Explanatory Note

The trend in Common Eider is dominated by The Netherlands, where largest part of the Wadden Sea population is breeding. Nests are mainly found in dune areas. The downward trend observed here from the late 1990s onwards was preceded by mass-starvation among wintering Eiders in 1999/2000 and attributed to depletion of mussel stocks by shellfish fisheries. Small populations in the Danish and Niedersachsen part of the Wadden Sea fluctuate from year to year, but point at an increase. As the species is difficult to monitor due to its breeding behaviour, some fluctuations might also reflect census problem or annual variation in the number of birds that actually breed.

Figures 4.4.3-4.4.6
The figures represent the trends of Common Eider in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figure 4.4.7 (right)
Total counts of Common Eider in the international Wadden Sea.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓ ↓	↓ ↓
(C) Denmark		↑ ↑	↑ ↑
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓ ↓	↓ ↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↑	—
(F) The Netherlands		↓ ↓	↓ ↓

↑ ↑ strong increase
 ↓ ↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain
 — data do not allow trend analysis

4.5 Red-breasted Merganser

Mergus serrator

02210

DK: Toppet Skallesluger D: Mittelsäger NL: Middelste Zaagbek

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Figures 4.5.1-4.5.2
The left figure represent the trend of Red-breasted Merganser in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis. The right figure shows the total count of Red-breasted Merganser in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

Explanatory Note

Red-breasted Merganser is only breeding in small numbers in the Wadden Sea, where it reaches the southern edge of its breeding range. Numbers fluctuate without a clear trend. Core breeding areas are situated in Schleswig-Holstein. In other parts of the Wadden Sea it is an accidental breeder.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		■	■
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		—	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		—	—
(F) The Netherlands		—	—

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable ■ uncertain — data do not allow trend analysis

Figures 4.5.3-4.5.6
The data about Red-breasted Merganser allow no trend analysis in the countries.

Figure 4.5.7
Total counts of Red-breasted Merganser in the international Wadden Sea.

4.6 Hen Harrier

02610

Circus cyaneus

DK: Blå Kærhøg D: Kornweihe NL: Blauwe Kiekendief

Figures 4.6.1-4.6.2
The left figure represent the trend of Hen Harrier in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.
The right figure shows the total count of Hen Harrier in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Explanatory Note

Breeding in Hen Harrier is restricted to The Netherlands and Niedersachsen, where it mainly inhabits the dune areas on the islands. In The Netherlands an ongoing decline has been observed from 1994 onwards. In Niedersachsen the species initially was able to maintain a high population level (resulting in an overall increase). However, recently, numbers are also going down here. Survival analyses and data from ring recoveries suggest that Hen Harrier especially face problems in their wintering areas, mainly outside of the Wadden Sea.

Figures 4.6.3-4.6.6
The figures represent the trends of Hen Harrier in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figure 4.6.7 (right)
Total counts of Hen Harrier in the international Wadden Sea.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓↓↓
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		—	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↗	↓
(F) The Netherlands		↓↓↓	↓↓↓

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↗ moderate increase
↘ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain — data do not allow trend analysis

4.7 Eurasian Oystercatcher

Haematopus ostralegus

04500

DK: Strandskade

D: Austernfischer NL: Scholekster

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Explanatory Note

Oystercatcher is one of the most abundant breeding birds in the Wadden Sea and a large proportion of the NW-European breeding population can be found here. Long term trends point at declines, starting earliest in Schleswig-Holstein and The Netherlands. The decline was initiated by the cold winter 1995/96 and low food stocks, as a result of depletion mainly by shellfish fisheries in the 1990s (in The Netherlands). Although fishery regulations meanwhile have changed, a population recovery has not occurred so far. Research has shown that the species has suffered from increased storm tides in the breeding season. Results from the new parameter breeding succes point at ongoing low reproduction rates in large parts of the Wadden Sea, suggesting further declines in near future.

Figures 4.7.1-4.7.2 The left figure represent the trend of Eurasian Oystercatcher in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis. The right figure shows the total count of Eurasian Oystercatcher in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figures 4.7.3-4.7.6 The figures represent the trends of Eurasian Oystercatcher in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		↓	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		↓	↓

↑ strong increase
 ↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain
 — data do not allow trend analysis

Figure 4.7.7 Total counts of Eurasian Oystercatcher in the international Wadden Sea.

4.8 Pied Avocet

04560

Recurvirostra avosetta

DK: Klyde

D: Säbelschnäbler

NL: Kluut

Figures 4.8.1–4.8.2
The left figure represent the trend of Pied Avocet in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.
The right figure shows the total count of Pied Avocet in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Explanatory Note

Avocet is one of the prime breeding bird species in the Wadden Sea, supporting a large share of the NW-European breeding population. The overall population shows a decline from 1999 onwards, being most pronounced in The Netherlands. On the other hand in Schleswig-Holstein numbers have remained stable for a long time, but recently start to decline as well. Due to its preference for silty mud flats, Avocet mainly breed on the mainland coast, where they locally suffer from high predation rates by mammalian predators. Besides, the species is susceptible to cold and stormy weather in the chick-rearing period in May and June, affecting chick survival. Data from the TMAP parameter breeding success point at low breeding success all over the Wadden Sea.

Figures 4.8.3–4.8.6
The figures represent the trends of Pied Avocet in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figure 4.8.7 (right)
Total counts of Pied Avocet in the international Wadden Sea.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		↓	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↔	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		↓↓	↓↓

↑ strong increase
 ↓ moderate decrease
 ↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
 ↔ stable
 — uncertain
 — data do not allow trend analysis

4.9 Great Ringed Plover

Charadrius hiaticula

04700

DK: Stor Præstekrave D: Sandregenpfeifer NL: Bontbekplevier

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Figures 4.9.1-4.9.2
The left figure represent the trend of Great Ringed Plover in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.
The right figure shows the total count of Great Ringed Plover in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

Explanatory Note

Great Ringed Plover is among the most declining breeding bird species in the Wadden Sea. In recent years the population fluctuates at a low level. The decline in the Wadden Sea coincides with declines elsewhere in the breeding range. In the Wadden Sea, losses have been often attributed to disturbance and reduced habitat dynamics on the preferred breeding sites at the beaches and lower dunes.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	—
(C) Denmark		↓	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓ ↓	—
(F) The Netherlands		↓	—

↑ strong increase
 ↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain
 — data do not allow trend analysis

Figure 4.9.7
Total counts of Great Ringed Plover in the international Wadden Sea.

4.10 Kentish Plover

04770

Charadrius alexandrinus

DK: Hvidbrystet Præstekrave D: Seeregenpfeifer NL: Strandplevier

Figures 4.10.1–4.10.2
The left figure represent the trend of Kentish Plover in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.
The right figure shows the total count of Kentish Plover in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Explanatory Note

The Wadden Sea represents the core breeding area for Kentish Plovers in NW-Europe. Ongoing declines have been observed from the mid 1990s onwards with highest rates of decline in Niedersachsen. Only in Denmark, the species is still thriving at islands like Rømø. The decline in other parts of the Wadden Sea seems to level off recently. Declines have not only been reported in the Wadden Sea, but also elsewhere in the breeding range. In the Wadden Sea, the species has faced limited habitat dynamics in coastal habitats (beaches and lower dunes) and increased disturbance by tourism.

Figures 4.10.3–4.10.6
The figures represent the trends of Kentish Plover in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figure 4.10.7 (right)
Total counts of Kentish Plover in the international Wadden Sea.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	→
(C) Denmark		↑	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓↓	↓↓
(F) The Netherlands		↓	—

↑ strong increase
 ↓ moderate decrease
 ↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
 → stable
 — uncertain
 — data do not allow trend analysis

4.11 Northern Lapwing

Vanellus vanellus

04930

DK: Vibe

D: Kiebitz

NL: Kievit

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Figures 4.11.1-4.11.2
The left figure represent the trend of Northern Lapwing in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.
The right figure shows the total count of Northern Lapwing in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

Explanatory Note

Northern Lapwing is a declining species in the Wadden Sea, although only in Denmark, Schleswig-Holstein and Niedersachsen. In the Dutch Wadden Sea the population has remained stable over the entire period. Farmland areas in the interior parts of The Netherlands, however, show declines as well, implicating that its Wadden Sea population is doing better. Preferred habitat is grassland, both behind the seawall and at salt marshes managed as such.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figures 4.11.3-4.11.6
The figures represent the trends of Northern Lapwing in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		↓	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		→	→

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain — data do not allow trend analysis

Figure 4.11.7
Total counts of Northern Lapwing in the international Wadden Sea.

4.12 Black-tailed Godwit

05320

Limosa limosa

DK: Stor Kobbersneppe

D: Uferschnepfe

NL: Grutto

Figures 4.12.1–4.12.2
The left figure represent the trend of Black-tailed Godwit in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.
The right figure shows the total count of Black-tailed Godwit in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Explanatory Note

Breeding Black-tailed Godwit in the Wadden Sea are mainly found in coastal grasslands behind the seawall, coastal wetlands, summer-polders and salt marshes. Numbers have gone down in all parts of the area. In The Netherlands, the population has remained stable over the past ten years. Also the rate of the long term decline has been slower than elsewhere in the Wadden Sea (cf. Northern Lapwing). Predation pressure and increased agricultural practices are among the most important causes for the observed trends.

Figures 4.12.3–4.12.6
The figures represent the trends of Black-tailed Godwit in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figure 4.12.7 (right)
Total counts of Black-tailed Godwit in the international Wadden Sea.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		↓	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		—	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		↓	→

↑ strong increase
 ↓ moderate decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
 — uncertain
 — data do not allow trend analysis

4.13 Eurasian Curlew

Numenius arquata

05410

DK: Stor Regnspove

D: GroÙer Brachvogel

NL: Wulp

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Figures 4.13.1-4.13.2 The left figure represent the trend of Eurasian Curlew in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis. The right figure shows the total count of Eurasian Curlew in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

Explanatory Note

Eurasian Curlew is a typical dune-breeding species in the Wadden Sea. Hence, it is mainly confined to the islands, especially those west of the River Elbe. The species is in decline, mainly due to losses in The Netherlands, where highest densities occur. This development has been attributed to vegetation succession in coastal dunes and negative impact of outdoor recreation. At the same time, birds have shifted from coastal dunes, to agricultural areas inland. Recently, the decline has halted and stable numbers are observed.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figures 4.13.3-4.13.6 The figures represent the trends of Eurasian Curlew in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	→
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		—	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		—	—
(F) The Netherlands		↓	→

↑ strong increase
 ↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain
 — data do not allow trend analysis

Figure 4.13.7 Total counts of Eurasian Curlew in the international Wadden Sea.

4.14 Common Redshank

05460

Tringa totanus

DK: Rødben

D: Rotschenkel

NL: Tureluur

Figures 4.14.1–4.14.2 The left figure represent the trend of Common Redshank in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis. The right figure shows the total count of Common Redshank in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Explanatory Note

Common Redshank preferably breed in salt marsh areas with tall vegetation, often associated with low-intensity management regime. The overall trend is negative. In Schleswig-Holstein numbers have remained stable over all years, albeit current numbers are lower than around 2000. In Niedersachsen and The Netherlands the population has stabilized recently, whereas in Denmark a sharp decline has occurred after 2006.

Figures 4.14.3–4.14.6 The figures represent the trends of Common Redshank in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figure 4.14.7 (right) Total counts of Common Redshank in the international Wadden Sea.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		↓	↓↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		→	→
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	→
(F) The Netherlands		↓	→

↑ strong increase
 ↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain
 — data do not allow trend analysis

4.15 Mediterranean Gull

Larus melanocephalus

05750

DK: Sorthovedet Måge D: Schwarzkopfmöve NL: Zwartkopmeeuw

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Figures 4.15.1-4.15.2 The left figure represent the trend of Mediterranean Gull in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis. The right figure shows the total count of Mediterranean Gull in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

Explanatory Note

Mediterranean Gull is a rather new breeding species to the Wadden Sea, and in line with developments in e.g. the Delta area, SW-Netherlands, numbers and distribution have also expanded in the Wadden Sea (though not as fast as elsewhere). In 1991 the species was only found in The Netherlands, in 1994 it colonized Niedersachsen and in 1996 Schleswig-Holstein and Denmark. After 2008 numbers have gone down to the level of the early 2000s. In this period the main colony on an island in the River Elbe was raided by predators. Elsewhere mainly scattered pairs are found breeding, often also associated with colonies of Black-headed Gull.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↑↑	—
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		—	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		—	→
(F) The Netherlands		—	—

↑↑ strong increase ↓↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
 ↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain — data do not allow trend analysis

Figure 4.15.7 Total counts of Mediterranean Gull in the international Wadden Sea.

4.16 Common Black-headed Gull

05820

Larus ridibundus

DK: Hættemåge

D: Lachmöwe

NL: Kokmeeuw

Figures 4.16.1–4.16.2
The left figure represent the trend of Common Black-headed Gull in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.
The right figure shows the total count of Common Black-headed Gull in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Explanatory Note

Black-headed Gull is one of the most abundant breeding birds in the Wadden Sea and a major part of the NW-European population is found here. Highest numbers breed west of the River Elbe. Largest colonies are situated in salt marshes and on remote islands. The trend is partly dominated by fluctuations, but points at downward numbers since 1991. Only in Schleswig-Holstein the population has remained stable, and increased after 2007. In Niedersachsen on the other hand, numbers also went down in the past 10 years. At least locally, colonies have been abandoned due to predation pressure, but other factors like food availability might affect population trends as well.

Figures 4.16.3–4.16.6
The figures represent the trends of Common Black-headed Gull in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figure 4.16.7 (right)
Total counts of Common Black-headed Gull in the international Wadden Sea.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	—
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		→	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		↓	—

↑ strong increase
 ↓ moderate decrease
 ↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
 → stable
 — uncertain
 — data do not allow trend analysis

4.17 Common Gull

Larus canus

05900

DK: Stormmåge

D: Sturmmöwe

NL: Stormmeeuw

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Figures 4.17.1-4.17.2 The left figure represent the trend of Common Gull in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis. The right figure shows the total count of Common Gull in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

Explanatory Note

Even if, the Wadden Sea is not a main breeding area for **Common Gull** in an international context, the species is thriving in most countries, resulting in a positive overall trend. Only in The Netherlands the species is in decline, especially after 2000. Breeding colonies are mainly found in coastal dune areas. It is not precisely known for what reason the population in The Netherlands is doing less well than elsewhere. In some years low reproductive rates have been recorded, but as the species is not part of the breeding success monitoring scheme, it is not known on what scale this occurs. Due to the declines in The Netherlands, and more recently also Niedersachsen and Denmark, the overall trend has become negative over the past 10 years.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figures 4.17.3-4.17.6 The figures represent the trends of Common Gull in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↑	↓
(C) Denmark		↑	↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↑	→
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↑↑	—
(F) The Netherlands		↓	↓↓

↑ ↑↑ strong increase ↓ ↓↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain — data do not allow trend analysis

Figure 4.17.7 Total count of Common Gull in the international Wadden Sea.

4.18 Lesser Black-backed Gull

05910

Larus fuscus

DK: Sildemåge D: Heringsmöwe NL: Kleine Mantelmeeuw

Figures 4.18.1–4.18.2
The left figure represent the trend of Lesser Black-backed Gull in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.
The right figure shows the total count of Lesser Black-backed Gull in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Explanatory Note

Lesser Black-backed Gull is among the fastest expanding species in the Wadden Sea. More recent data from Schleswig-Holstein, Niedersachsen and The Netherlands point at a stabilization. Data from the breeding success monitoring in The Netherlands show high chick mortality due to limited food provision. Hence, the increase observed so far might reverse in a drop in numbers, but this has to be confirmed by further counts and continued monitoring of breeding success. In an international context, a large proportion of the NW-European population is breeding in the Wadden Sea.

Figures 4.18.3–4.18.6
The figures represent the trends of Lesser Black-backed Gull in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figure 4.18.7 (right)
Total counts of Lesser Black-backed Gull in the international Wadden Sea.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↑↑	↑
(C) Denmark		↑↑	↑
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↑↑	→
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↑↑	—
(F) The Netherlands		↑	—

↑↑ strong increase
 ↓↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain
 — data do not allow trend analysis

4.19 Herring Gull

Larus argentatus

05920

DK: Sølvmåge

D: Silbermöwe

NL: Zilvermeeuw

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Figures 4.19.1–4.19.2
The left figure represent the trend of Herring Gull in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.
The right figure shows the total count of Herring Gull in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

Explanatory Note

Herring Gull often breeds in mixed colonies with Lesser Black-backed. Compared to the latter species, it feeds more extensively on the mud flats in most areas. Populations have declined in the whole Wadden Sea, mainly due to losses in The Netherlands and Niedersachsen, which are the core breeding areas. In The Netherlands the species has suffered from depletion of mussel stocks by shellfish fisheries. Moreover, they have benefited from rubbish dumps earlier, which today are all closed and not available as food resource anymore. The smaller populations in Denmark and the colonies in Schleswig-Holstein are performing better, and especially in Denmark have shown a strong increase. Recent counts in Schleswig-Holstein suggest some decline, whereas in The Netherlands the negative trend has stabilized.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		↑	↑
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		→	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓↓
(F) The Netherlands		↓	→

↑↑ strong increase ↓↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
 ↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain — data do not allow trend analysis

Figure 4.19.7
Total counts of Herring Gull in the international Wadden Sea.

4.20 Great Black-backed Gull

06000

Larus marinus

DK: Svartbag D: Mantelmöve NL: Grote Mantelmeeuw

Figures 4.20.1–4.20.2 The left figure represent the trend of Great Black-backed Gull in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis. The right figure shows the total count of Great Black-backed Gull in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Explanatory Note

Great Black-backed Gull is expanding its breeding range in southwestern direction. Hence, its distribution in the Wadden Sea has become less scattered and numbers have shown an overall increase since 1991. This trend is most pronounced in Schleswig-Holstein, where also highest numbers are found. The small Danish population shows considerable fluctuations.

Figures 4.20.3–4.20.6 The figures represent the trends of Great Black-backed Gull in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figure 4.20.7 (right) Total counts of Great Black-backed Gull in the international Wadden Sea.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↑↑	↑
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↑↑	↑
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		—	—
(F) The Netherlands		—	—

↑↑ strong increase
 ↓↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain
 — data do not allow trend analysis

4.21 Gull-billed Tern

Gelochelidon nilotica

06050

DK: Sandterne D: Lachseeschwalbe NL: Lachstern

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Figures 4.21.1-4.21.2 The left figure represent the trend of Gull-billed Tern in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis. The right figure shows the total count of Gull-billed Tern in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

Explanatory Note

The Wadden Sea represents the only breeding area for Gull-billed Terns in the Wadden Sea. Initially this was confined to Denmark, but since the 1970s this has shifted to Schleswig-Holstein, where the species is currently breeding in a colony in Neufelder Koog in the Elbe estuary, associated with Black-headed Gull, Common Tern and Arctic Tern. Earlier settlements in the Niedersachsen part of the Elbe estuary have been deserted now. Due to fluctuating numbers, the overall trend is not clear, although current numbers are lower compared to the 1990s.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		—	—
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		—	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	—
(F) The Netherlands		—	—

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain — data do not allow trend analysis

Figure 4.21.7 Total count of Gull-billed Tern in the international Wadden Sea.

4.22 Sandwich Tern

06110

Sterna sandvicensis

DK: Splitterne

D: Brandseeschwalbe

NL: Grote Stern

Figures 4.22.1-4.22.2
The left figure represent the trend of Sandwich Tern in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.
The right figure shows the total count of Sandwich Tern in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Explanatory Note

Sandwich Tern is entirely breeding on remote islands like Griend (The Netherlands) and Norderoog (Schleswig-Holstein). The colonies in the Wadden Sea represent a large part of the NW-European breeding population. The overall trend is classified as stable. The small and growing population in Denmark probably received some input from Schleswig-Holstein, where the colonies have experienced declines (notably after 2000). Exchange between colonies has also been observed elsewhere in The Wadden Sea. After 2011 a sudden decline has occurred in The Netherlands, especially at the large colony of Griend.

Figures 4.22.3-4.22.6
The figures represent the trends of Sandwich Tern in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figure 4.22.7 (right)
Total counts of Sandwich Tern in the international Wadden Sea.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	—
(C) Denmark		↑↑	↑↑
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓↓	↓↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		—	—
(F) The Netherlands		↑	—

↑↑ strong increase ↓↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain — data do not allow trend analysis

4.23 Common Tern

Sterna hirundo

06150

DK: Fjordterne

D: Flußseeschwalbe

NL: Visdief

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Figures 4.23.1-4.23.2
The left figure represent the trend of Common Tern in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.
The right figure shows the total count of Common Tern in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

Explanatory Note

Breeding Common Terns are widespread in the Wadden Sea and inhabit different habitats, including harbour areas, rooftops of buildings and other anthropogenic habitats. The species is only doing well in Schleswig-Holstein, whereas in other countries populations have gone down, especially in Denmark. Hence, overall trend is negative. Often, poor food availability has been put forward as main background for declines, but other factors as predation pressure (mainland colonies), reduced habitat dynamics and losses due to storm tides in the breeding season are probably operating as well.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figures 4.23.3-4.23.6
The figures represent the trends of Common Tern in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		↓	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		—	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	—
(F) The Netherlands		↓	↓

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain — data do not allow trend analysis

Figure 4.23.7
Total counts of Common Tern in the international Wadden Sea.

4.24 Arctic Tern

06160

Sterna paradisaea

DK: Havterne D: Küstenseeschwalbe NL: Noordse Stern

Figures 4.24.1–4.24.2
The left figure represent the trend of Arctic Tern in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.
The right figure shows the total count of Arctic Tern in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Explanatory Note

Arctic Tern has a more northerly breeding range in Europe and therefore largest colonies are found north of the River Elbe. Large colonies are mainly situated in Schleswig-Holstein. Compared to Common Tern (where it sometimes associates with), they prefer more sparsely vegetated breeding sites and are found less in anthropogenic habitats. Apart from Denmark and Schleswig-Holstein, populations in all parts of the Wadden Sea have declined. In The Netherlands a pronounced negative trend continued in the past 10 years.

Figures 4.24.3–4.24.6
The figures represent the trends of Arctic Tern in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figure 4.24.7 (right)
Total counts of Arctic Tern in the international Wadden Sea.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		→	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		→	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	—
(F) The Netherlands		↓	↓

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain — data do not allow trend analysis

4.25 Little Tern

Sterna albifrons

06240

DK: Dværgterne D: Zwergseeschwalbe NL: Dwergstern

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Figures 4.25.1-4.25.2
The left figure represent the trend of Little Tern in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.
The right figure shows the total count of Little Tern in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

Explanatory Note

Little Tern predominantly breeds on the islands, where it inhabits beaches, sand pits and primary dunes. At many sites, protective measures are taken to keep colonies undisturbed from public. After an initial increase in the 1990s, the species is showing negative trends in the past decade, leading to an overall stable trend classification. However, in Schleswig-Holstein and Niedersachsen, both supporting core breeding sites, significant declines have occurred. In Denmark (increase) and The Netherlands (increase) populations show more annual variation in numbers. In both countries, number tend to decline recently, which is confirmed by data collected in 2012 and 2013.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figures 4.25.3-4.25.6
The figures represent the trends of Little Tern in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	—
(C) Denmark		↑	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	—
(F) The Netherlands		↑	—

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain — data do not allow trend analysis

Figure 4.25.7
Total counts of Little Tern in the international Wadden Sea.

4.26 Short-eared Owl

07680

Asio flammeus

DK: Mosehornugl

D: Sumpfohreule

NL: Velduil

Figures 4.26.1–4.26.2
The left figure represent the trend of Short-eared Owl in the international Wadden Sea from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis. The right figure shows the total count of Short-eared Owl in the international Wadden Sea and in the countries in 2006.

(A) Overall trend in the International Wadden Sea

Explanatory Note

Short-eared Owls prefer open dunes and heathland as breeding habitat, often in association with feeding areas in grassland or salt marshes. It has its strongholds west of the River Elbe and its distribution is mainly confined to the islands. Numbers usually fluctuate and partly show synchronous peaks throughout the Wadden Sea, in association with years with high abundance of voles. The overall trend is negative, especially due to the declines in The Netherlands (more recently also Niedersachsen).

Figures 4.26.3–4.26.6
The figures represent the trends of Short-eared Owl in the countries from 1991 to 2011 and show annual indices of the breeding population relative to 1996 (=100, shown by the red dot). Annual index values are expressed at the y-axis.

(B) Denmark

(C) Schleswig-Holstein

(D) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(E) The Netherlands

Figure 4.26.7 (right)
Total counts of Short-eared Owl in the international Wadden Sea.

Area	Period	1991 - 2011	2002 - 2011
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		—	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	—
(F) The Netherlands		↓	—

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain — data do not allow trend analysis

5 Total counts rare species

For 7 breeding bird species of the JMBB program data do not allow trend analysis. Nevertheless, to give an impression on numbers of these bird species the total count numbers are given. They show that, apart from 'new' species like Little Egret and Barnacle Goose, most rare species have become rarer in recent years. Ruddy Turnstone and Little Gull have deserted the Wadden Sea.

It is likely that Dunlin and especially Ruff will become extinct as well.

Figures 5.1-5.7
Total counts of rare breeding bird species in the international Wadden Sea.

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Annex 1 Species according to habitats and food

Species	Breeding habitats				Food guilds			
	coastal grasslands	beach & outer sands	dunes	salt marsh	voles/birds	fish (pelagic)	fish & shrimps (general)	invertebrates
Great Cormorant		x					x	
Eurasian Spoonbill		x					x	
Shelduck			x					x
Common Eider		x						x
Red-breasted Merganser		x					x	
Hen Harrier			x		x			
Eurasian Oystercatcher				x				x
Pied Avocet				x				x
Great Ringed Plover		x						x
Kentish Plover		x						x
Northern Lapwing	x							x
Black-tailed Godwit	x							x
Eurasian Curlew			x					x
Common Redshank				x				x
Mediterranean Gull				x				x
Common Black-headed Gull				x				x
Common Gull			x					x
Lesser Black-backed Gull			x				x	
Herring Gull			x					x
Great Black-backed Gull			x				x	
Gull-billed Tern				x				
Sandwich Tern		x				x		
Common Tern		x				x		
Arctic Tern		x				x		
Little Tern		x				x		
Short-eared Owl			x		x			
Total number of species	2	10	8	6	2	4	5	14

Table A1.1
Selection of species according to breeding habitats and food guilds.

Photo: Klaus Janke

Annex 2 Counting units in the Wadden Sea

Figure A.2.1
The Wadden Sea Area
including delimitations
of all counting units and
counting sites.

Annex 3 List of census areas

Table A.3.1
List of census areas in the
Wadden Sea that are used to
assess trends in this report.

Country	Census region	Region name	Trilateral code	Name census area	Size in ha
The Netherlands					
NL	1	Texel	11001	De Schorren	47
NL	1	Texel	11002	De Slufter	96
NL	1	Texel	11003	De Bol/Wagejot	88
NL	1	Texel	11004	Westerduinen/Bleekersvallei	304
NL	1	Texel	11005	De Geul	35
NL	1	Texel	11006	Prins Hendrik polder	98
NL	2	Vlieland	12020	Kroon's polders	184
NL	2	Vlieland	12021	Vallei van het Veen	223
NL	2	Vlieland	12022	Richel	223
NL	3	Griend	12023	Griend	21
NL	4	Terschelling	12024	Noordvaarder	207
NL	4	Terschelling	12025	Waterplak	166
NL	4	Terschelling	12026	Polder Hoorn	83
NL	4	Terschelling	12027	Douwkesplak	192
NL	4	Terschelling	12028	Vierde Duintjes, dunes	265
NL	4	Terschelling	12029	Vierde Duintjes, salt marsh (included in 12028)	
NL	5	Ameland	12030	Lange Duinen, noord	14
NL	5	Ameland	12031	polder near Hollum	178
NL	5	Ameland	12032	Hagedoornveld	126
NL	5	Ameland	12033	Nieuwlandsreid	366
NL	6	Engelsmanplaat/'t Rif	12034	Engelsmanplaat/'t Rif	775
NL	7	Schiermonnikoog	12035	Bancks polder	33
NL	7	Schiermonnikoog	12036	Oosterkwelder	764
NL	8	Rottumeroog en -plaat	13050	Rottumerplaat	723
NL	8	Rottumeroog en -plaat	13069	Rottumeroog	202
NL	8	Rottumeroog en -plaat	13070	Zuiderduin	38
NL	9	oast Noord-Holland	11007	Balgzand salt marsh	67
NL	9	coast Noord-Holland	11010	Wieringen 1 Westerland	17
NL	9	coast Noord-Holland	11011	Wieringen 2 Stroe	5
NL	9	coast Noord-Holland	11012	Wieringen 3 Vatrop	7
NL	9	coast Noord-Holland	11009	Stroeërkoog	58
NL	10	coast Friesland	12037	Blija zomerpolder Et kwelder	218
NL	10	coast Friesland	12038	Holwerd-oost	116
NL	10	coast Friesland	12039	Paesummerlannen	168
NL	10	coast Friesland	12040	Polder De Band	122
NL	11	coast Groningen	13065	Julianapolder	51
NL	11	coast Groningen	13066	Linthorst-Homanpolder	38
NL	11	coast Groningen	13067	Noordpolder	55
NL	11	coast Groningen	13068	Lauwerpolder	29
NL	12	Dollart-Außenems	13053	Polder Breebaart	68
NL	12	Dollart-Außenems	13059	Dollard 1 CCP km 9 Wa	38
NL	12	Dollart-Außenems	13060	Dollard 2 CCP km 7 Wb	37
NL	12	Dollart-Außenems	13061	Dollard 3 CCP km 4 la	27
NL	12	Dollart-Außenems	13062	Dollard 4 CCP km 3 lf	43
NL	12	Dollart-Außenems	13063	Dollard 5 RWP km 1 llb	32
NL	12	Dollart-Außenems	13064	Dollard 6 RWP km 0 lie	21
NL	12	Dollart-Außenems	13055	Carel Coenraadpolder akker	84
Niedersachsen					
Nds	12	Dollart-Außenems	21020	Bohrinsel Süd	24
Nds	12	Dollart-Außenems	21021	Buttje Pad Süd	41
Nds	13	Leybucht	21022	Buscherheller	64

Country	Census region	Region name	Trilateral code	Name census area	Size in ha
Nds	13	Leybucht	21023	Mittelplate	65
Nds	13	Leybucht	21024	Hauener Hooge	52
Nds	15	Juist-Memmert	21005	Memmert	261
Nds	15	Juist-Memmert	21033	Aussichtsdüne, Augustenhöhe /Juist	115
Nds	16	Norderney-Baltrum-Langeoog	21026	Schlopp-Ost / Norderney	40
Nds	16	Norderney-Baltrum-Langeoog	21027	Peilbake / Norderney	85
Nds	16	Norderney-Baltrum-Langeoog	21032	Pyrolatal West, Pyrolatal / Langeoog	132
Nds	17	Norderland-Harlingerland	21025	Westerneßmer Vorland - Teichbecken	56
Nds	18	Elisabeth-Außengroden	21010	Vorland	180
Nds	18	Elisabeth-Außengroden	21011	Vorland W	150
Nds	19	Spieker./Wanger./Minsener Oog	21003	Minsener Oog	125
Nds	19	Spieker./Wanger./Minsener Oog	21028	Franzosenschanze /Spiekeroog West	63
Nds	19	Spieker./Wanger./Minsener Oog	21029	Legde Heller West / Spiekeroog Ost	98
Nds	20	Mellum	21004	Mellum	336
Nds	22	Jadebusen	21016	Vorland S, Vorland N	300
Nds	22	Jadebusen	21017	Vorland	330
Nds	24	Wurster Küste	21007	Vorland N, Vorland S, Vorland Sommerpolder N, Vorland Sommerpolder S	970
Nds	25	Neuwerk-Scharhörn	22001	Scharhörn	18
Nds	25	Neuwerk-Scharhörn	22002	Nigehörn	20
Nds	25	Neuwerk-Scharhörn	22003	Neuwerk Vorland O	85
Nds	26	Elbe Niedersachsen	21030	Baljer Loch, Außendeich Nordkehdingen West	59
Nds	26	Elbe Niedersachsen	21031	Wildvogelreservat Nordkehdingen	59
Schleswig-Holstein					
SH	28	Salt marshes in Dithmarschen	23001	Vorland Dieksander Koog Nord	155
SH	28	Salt marshes in Dithmarschen	23002	Vorland Friedrichskoog/Aug. Vikt. Koog	143
SH	28	Salt marshes in Dithmarschen	23003	Helmsand	1027
SH	28	Salt marshes in Dithmarschen	23004	Vorland Hedwigenkoog	219
SH	29	Trischen	23014	Trischen	1549
SH	35	Salt marshes in Eiderstedt	23005	Vorland St. Peter	245
SH	35	Salt marshes in Eiderstedt	23006	Tuemlauer Bucht	72
SH	35	Salt marshes in Eiderstedt	23007	Westerhever-Vorland	27
SH	35	Salt marshes in Eiderstedt	23008	Vorland Norderheverkoog	181
SH	36	Salt marshes in Nordfriesland	23009	Vorland Schobuell	328
SH	36	Salt marshes in Nordfriesland	23010	Vorland Nordstrand Sued	60
SH	36	Salt marshes in Nordfriesland	23011	Hamburger Hallig	75
SH	36	Salt marshes in Nordfriesland	23012	Vorland Marienkoog	149
SH	36	Salt marshes in Nordfriesland	23013	Vorland Rickelsbüller Koog	528
SH	37	Halligen	23015	Hallig Norderoog	377
SH	37	Halligen	23016	Hallig Langeneß	61
SH	37	Halligen	23017	Hallig Langeneß Vorland	367
SH	39	Amrum	23019	Amrum-Odde	561
SH	40	Föhr	23018	Foehrer Vorland	256
SH	41	Sylt	23020	Sylt Sandinseln Keitum	11
SH	41	Sylt	23021	Sylt Morsum-Odde	119
Denmark					
DK	43	Rejsby-Ballum salt marshes	31014	Ballum Forland	97
DK	43	Rejsby-Ballum salt marshes	32016	Råhede Vade	58
DK	44	Ribe-Darum salt marshes	32015	Jedsted Forland	133
DK	45	Ho Bugt coast Skallingen	32013	Skallingen	223
DK	45	Ho Bugt coast Skallingen	32014	Tarphage Enge	155
DK	46	Langli	32001	Langli	97
DK	47	Fano	32007	Grønningen	92
DK	49	Romo-Jordsand	31006	Stormengene	55
DK	49	Romo-Jordsand	31011	Rømø Nørreland	151
DK	51	Ballumarsken	31007	Husum Enge	224

Annex 4 Counting coverage of census areas

Figure A.4.1 - A.4.4
Counting coverage of 102
international agreed census
areas.

Annex 5 Species list

Table A.4.1
List of breeding bird species
monitored in the Trilateral
Monitoring and Assessment
Program (TMAP) sorted by
Euring code.

Euring	English name	Scientific name	Dansk navn	Deutscher Name	Nederlandse naam
00720	Great Cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	Skarv	Kormoran	Aalscholver
01440	Eurasian Spoonbill	<i>Platalea leucorodia</i>	Skestork	Löffler	Lepelaar
01190	Little Egret*	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	Silkehejre	Seidenreier	Kleine Zilverreiger
01670	Barnacle Goose*	<i>Branta leucopsis</i>	Bramgås	Nonnengans	Brandgans
01730	Common Shelduck	<i>Tadorna tadorna</i>	Gravand	Brandgans	Bergeend
01790	Eurasian Wigeon*	<i>Anas penelope</i>	Pibeand	Pfeifente	Smient
01890	Northern Pintail*	<i>Anas acuta</i>	Spidsand	Spießente	Pijlstaart
02060	Common Eider	<i>Somateria mollissima</i>	Ederfugl	Eiderente	Eidereend
02210	Red-breasted Merganser	<i>Mergus serrator</i>	Toppet Skallesluger	Mittelsäger	Middelste Zaagbek
02610	Hen Harrier	<i>Circus cyaneus</i>	Blå Kærhøg	Kornweihe	Blauwe Kiekendief
04500	Eurasian Oystercatcher	<i>Haematopus ostralegus</i>	Strandskade	Austernfischer	Scholekster
04560	Pied Avocet	<i>Recurvirostra avosetta</i>	Klyde	Säbelschnäbler	Kluut
04700	Great Ringed Plover	<i>Charadrius hiaticula</i>	Stor Præstekrave	Sandregenpfeifer	Bontbekplevier
04770	Kentish Plover	<i>Charadrius alexandrinus</i>	Hvidbrystet Præstekrave	Seeregenpfeifer	Strandplevier
04930	Northern Lapwing	<i>Vanellus vanellus</i>	Vibe	Kiebitz	Kievit
05120	Dunlin*	<i>Calidris alpina</i>	Almindelig Ryle	Alpenstrandläufer	Bonte Strandloper
05170	Ruff*	<i>Philomachus pugnax</i>	Brushane	Kampfläufer	Kemphaan
05190	Common Snipe*	<i>Gallinago gallinago</i>	Dobbeltbekkasin	Bekassine	Watersnip
05320	Black-tailed Godwit	<i>Limosa limosa</i>	Stor Kobbersneppe	Uferschnepfe	Grutto
05410	Eurasian Curlew	<i>Numenius arquata</i>	Stor Regnspove	Großer Brachvogel	Wulp
05460	Common Redshank	<i>Tringa totanus</i>	Rødben	Rotschenkel	Tureluur
05610	Ruddy Turnstone*	<i>Arenaria interpres</i>	Stenvender	Steinwälzer	Steenloper
05750	Mediterranean Gull	<i>Larus melanocephalus</i>	Sorthovedet Måge	Schwarzkopfmöwe	Zwartkopmeeuw
05780	Little Gull*	<i>Larus minutus</i>	Dværgmåge	Zwergmöwe	Dwergmeeuw
05820	Common Black-headed Gull	<i>Larus ridibundus</i>	Hættemåge	Lachmöwe	Kokmeeuw
05900	Common Gull	<i>Larus canus</i>	Stormmåge	Sturmmöwe	Stormmeeuw
05910	Lesser Black-backed Gull	<i>Larus fuscus</i>	Sildemåge	Heringsmöwe	Kleine Mantelmeeuw
05920	Herring Gull	<i>Larus argentatus</i>	Sølvmåge	Silbermöwe	Zilvermeeuw
06000	Great Black-backed Gull	<i>Larus marinus</i>	Svartbag	Mantelmöwe	Grote Mantelmeeuw
06050	Gull-billed Tern	<i>Gelochelidon nilotica</i>	Sandterne	Lachseeschwalbe	Lachstern
06110	Sandwich Tern	<i>Sterna sandvicensis</i>	Splitterne	Brandseeschwalbe	Grote Stern
06150	Common Tern	<i>Sterna hirundo</i>	Fjordterne	Flußseeschwalbe	Visdief
06160	Arctic Tern	<i>Sterna paradisaea</i>	Havterne	Küstenseeschwalbe	Noordse Stern
06240	Little Tern	<i>Sterna albifrons</i>	Dværgterne	Zwergseeschwalbe	Dwergstern
07680	Short-eared Owl	<i>Asio flammeus</i>	Mosehornugl	Sumpfohreule	Velduil

* Species where data do not allow trend analysis

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